

ON THE REACTIVE CHAIN-LENGTH OF STARCH (AMYLOSE) SYNTHESISED BY MUSCLE PHOSPHORYLASE

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Hanes observed that equilibria in phosphorylase systems were unaffected by alterations in the concentrations of starch. He inferred therefrom that starch solutions might contain some component in a highly disaggregated condition which may be chemically active and this component was maintained in a state of saturation. Since direct chemical analysis is not possible, we have tried to approach the problem of determining the nature of this component from theoretical side based on a new theory of phosphorylase action, recently put forward by the author.

In considering the equilibria in phosphorylase systems, Hanes (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1940, B, 129, 205) observed "A point of interest is that the equilibrium is not perceptibly affected by alterations in the concentration of starch. This would seem to indicate that the effective concentration of starch is independent of the total concentration. A possible explanation may be that the phase of the colloidal system in which the reaction occurs is maintained in a state of saturation in respect to a form of starch in true solution or in a highly disaggregated condition". It will be highly interesting if we can get some clue as to the nature of this component. Evidently, however, in a complex system like that of starch, it is futile to expect that a direct chemical analysis will be of any avail.

Now, synthesis of polysaccharide from glucose-1-phosphate is represented by the equation,

It has been shown in a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 193) that on the assumption that the reaction as written above is catalysed in the direction from left to right by the uncharged forms of the enzyme ($\overset{+}{R}$ or HROH), whereas the reverse by the anions ROH⁻, the ratio of the inorganic phosphate/organic phosphate (*i.e.* F/P) works out to be

$$k_0 \frac{\alpha}{\beta^n}$$

where k_0 = constant,

α = mol. fraction of the enzyme in the form HROH

β = " " " " " " ROH⁻

It may be emphasised at the very outset that the value of 'n' will not necessarily be identical with the chain-length *i.e.* the number of glucose residues in the unit chain of the polysaccharide isolated. It is reasonable that 'n' corresponds to that component of starch system referred to by Hanes (*loc. cit.*) which will be effective in chemical reactions and must be used in mass law equations. 'n' may

therefore stand for what we may call the "reactive chain-length of the polyelectrolyte".

$$\text{Now, } F/P = k_0 \frac{\alpha}{\beta^n} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

taking logarithm

$$\ln (F/P) = \ln k_0 + \ln \alpha - \frac{1}{n} \ln \beta$$

differentiating with respect to $[H^+]$.

$$\frac{P}{F} \cdot \frac{d(F/P)}{d[H^+]} = 0 + \frac{1}{\alpha} \cdot \frac{d\alpha}{d[H^+]} - \frac{1}{n} \cdot \frac{1}{\beta} \cdot \frac{d\beta}{d[H^+]}$$

since, however, α has, in the regions of pH near the iso-electric, a maximum value $\frac{d\alpha}{d[H^+]} = 0$, also we may replace $\frac{1}{\beta} \cdot \frac{d\beta}{d[H^+]}$

by its approximate value $-\frac{l}{[H^+]}$ (see *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 193).

Therefore,

$$\frac{P}{F} \cdot \frac{d(F/P)}{d[H^+]} = \frac{l}{n[H^+]} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

Now, since (P/F) values are known, as also F/P as a function of pH , we can calculate $d(F/P)/dH$ for,

$$\frac{d(F/P)}{d[H^+]} = \frac{d(F/P)}{d \log [H^+]} \cdot \frac{d \log [H^+]}{d[H^+]} = -\frac{d(F/P)}{d(pH)} \cdot \frac{1}{[H^+]} \cdot \frac{1}{2.303}$$

also we can calculate ' v ', which may equal the valence of the enzyme protein, from the mobility data of Green (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1945, 158, 315).

Knowing these values we can find out the value of ' n ' from equation (2).

Calculation of the Valence of Phosphorylase-a (Muscle).—The relation between the charge and mobility of a sphere is given by Abramson, Moyer and Gorin ("Electrophoresis of Proteins", Chap. IV., p 123, equation 52) as

$$Q = \frac{6\pi\eta r (1 + \kappa r + \kappa r_i) v}{f(\kappa r) (1 + \kappa r_i)} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (a)$$

where, v = mobility in cm/sec/volt/cm; Q = charge in coulombs per molecule; η = viscosity; r = radius of the sphere; r_i = "average" radius of ions in the ion atmosphere; $\frac{1}{\kappa}$ = thickness of the double layer.

$$f(\kappa r) = \left\{ 1 + \frac{(\kappa r)^2}{16} - \frac{5}{48} (\kappa r)^3 - \frac{(\kappa r)^4}{96} + \frac{(\kappa r)^5}{96} - e^{-\kappa r} \left[\frac{12}{96} (\kappa r)^4 - \frac{(\kappa r)^6}{96} \right] \int_{\kappa}^{\kappa r} \frac{e^{-t}}{t} dt \right\}$$

It is known, however, that the frictional ratio (f/f_0) for phosphorylase-a from muscle is somewhat higher than unity, but in view of the work of Adair and Adair (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1936, B, 120, 422) on the density of protein crystals, higher

frictional ratios may be due to hydration. For this reason as also for simplicity, we may take the enzyme molecules as approximately spherical for our present treatment.

Again, the radius of the protein sphere is given by the relation.

$$r = \frac{K T}{6 \pi \eta D}$$

where,

K = Boltzmann constant ; T = absolute temperature ; η = viscosity ;
 D = diffusion constant.

From the data of Green and Cori (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1943, 151, 27), therefore,

$$r = \frac{(1.372 \times 10^{-10}) \times 293.1}{6 \times 3.142 \times 0.01118 \times 3.5 \times 10^{-7}} = 54.52 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm.}$$

The value of κ at μ (ionic strength) = 0.1 is

$$\kappa = \sqrt{0.1} \{3.06 \times 10^{-8}\} = 1.033 \times 10^7 \text{ cm}^{-1}.$$

Therefore,

$$\kappa r = (1.033 \times 10^7) (54.52 \times 10^{-8}) = 5.63$$

from Gorin's Table of values of $6/f(\kappa r)$ for various values of κr (Abramson, *et al.* "Electrophoresis of proteins" p 121),

$6/f(\kappa r)$ corresponding to 5.6 is = 5.133.

The average radius of electrolytic ions r_i is taken to be = 2.5×10^{-8} and $\kappa r_i = 0.258$.

Substituting these values in equation (a) and remembering that the valence of the protein γ (the number of excess positive or negative charges per molecule in electronic units) would be obtained by multiplying v by the factor

$$(300/4.8 \times 10^{-10})$$

we get,

$$V = \frac{5.133 \times 3.142 \times 0.01118 \times 54.52 \times 10^{-8} \times (1 + 5.6 + 0.26) \times v \times 300}{1.26 \times 4.80 \times 10^{-10}}$$

$$= 3.345 \times 10^5 \times v$$

thus l is $= 3.345 \times v \times 10^5$

Again from equation (2)

$$(P/F) \cdot \frac{d(F/P)}{d[H^+]} = \frac{l}{n [H^+]}$$

and since

$$\frac{d(F/P)}{d[H^+]} = - \frac{d(F/P)}{d(pH)} \cdot \frac{1}{[H^+]} \cdot \frac{1}{2.303}$$

therefore,

$$(P/F) \times -\frac{d(F/P)}{d(pH)} \cdot \frac{1}{[H^+]} \cdot \frac{1}{2.303} = \frac{l}{n[H^+]}$$

or,

$$(P/F) = -l \cdot \frac{2.303}{n} \cdot \frac{1}{m} \quad \text{where } m = \frac{d(F/P)}{d(pH)}$$

$$= \frac{-3.345 \times (v \times 10^5) \times 2.3}{mn}$$

If therefore we construct a graph (P/F) against $(v \times 10^5)$ i.e., mobility $\times 10^5$, the slope of the straight line would be

$$= \frac{3.3 \times 2.3}{mn}$$

From the actual graph (Fig. 1) it is found to be $-\frac{1}{9.3}$.

$$\text{Therefore, } n = -\frac{9.3 \times 3.3 \times 2.3}{m}$$

Also from the straight line (F/P) against pH (Fig. 2),

$$m = \frac{d(F/P)}{d(pH)} = -1.7,$$

which when put in the above equation, gives

$$n = \frac{9.3 \times 3.3 \times 2.3}{1.7} = 41.6.$$

Thus the active component of starch referred to by Hanes (*loc. cit.*) would be (glucose anhydride) ≈ 40 .

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

It has been observed (*Ann. Rev. Biochem.*, 1944, 13, 63) that starch may contain isomaltose linkings to the extent of one per 15-20 maltose linkings; also all starch fractions give rise to β -maltose with β -amylase (Frecman and Hopkins, *Biochem. J.*, 1936, 30, 451). One is therefore tempted to consider in view of the

fact that glucose-1-phosphate contains an α -linking, whether the occurrence of β -maltose linkages may not be responsible for the observed value of 'n'.

D I S C U S S I O N

In deducing the relation,

$$\frac{1}{\beta} \cdot \frac{d\beta}{d[H^+]} = - \frac{l}{[H^+]}$$

(Rai Chaudhury, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 193) it will be found that we have neglected the variation of 'l' with p_H . But it is clear from the mobility- p_H curve (Green, *loc. cit.*) that in the regions near about the neutral, it is very flat *i.e.*, for large variations in $[H^+]$, 'l' changes by only a small amount. Hence omission of the term containing $\frac{dl}{d[H^+]}$ may not involve any serious error.

Next, we are required to add a few explanatory words about the action of muscle phosphorylase. It is known that the equilibrium

does not obtain (Rai Chaudhury, *loc. cit.*).

How can then our derivations be expected to hold true? It may be recalled, however, that glucose-1-phosphate under the influence of muscle enzyme gives rise to a starch-like (amylose) polysaccharide with a chain length of 200 glucose units. Now, this synthetic polysaccharide can react with inorganic phosphate to give rise to glucose-1-phosphate. It stands to reason therefore that a true equilibrium such as synthetic polysaccharide + inorganic phosphate $\rightleftharpoons$ glucose-1-phosphate actually takes place. From what has been stated earlier in the introductory portions, we may extend the idea further and make out a scheme as follows:

Lastly, we must add that the use of the experimental data of 'phosphorylase-a' has been deliberately made since 'phosphorylase-b' which is probably formed by the scission of adenylic acid from 'phosphorylase-a' is never active without adenylic acid.

In conclusion, I beg to offer my grateful thanks to Dr. D. M. Bose, our Director, for the constant interest and encouragement that I receive from him.